

Revolutionizing Learning: Unraveling the Transformative Force of Kenya's Competence-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.)

Mutai R. Kipsang^{1*}, Liu Xiaoguang²

¹School of public administration, Nanjing Agricultural University, China

Abstract: This study aims to comprehensively examine the impact of the educational paradigm shift, with a specific focus on the Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.) in the Kenyan education system. Therefore, this research employs a mixed-methods research approach to investigate the implementation of the C.B.C. and identify the challenges encountered during the adoption of this transformative curriculum.

The study analyzes the resultant outcomes and assesses the effectiveness of this new educational approach in reshaping the educational landscape in Kenya. The findings of this study can have a significant impact on the formulation of educational policy and the improvement of instructional practices. Therefore, this study will contribute to the enhancement of student outcomes in the country, thus providing a clear pathway for an illuminated future for the Kenyan education system.

Keywords: Competence-based curriculum, Education paradigm shift, Kenyan education system, and Educational impact,

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 30 November, 2023; **Published:** 26 December, 2023

How to cite this article: Mutai .R.K & Liu Xiaoguang (2023). *Revolutionizing Learning: Unraveling the Transformative Force of Kenya's Competence-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.)*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(11), 116-134. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10431030>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Education is undergoing a profound transformation, driven by the need to equip students with the skills and competencies necessary for success in the 21st century. One such transformative approach is the Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.), which emphasizes the development of students' abilities to perform specific tasks, known as competencies, within a set of defined standards. This shift in educational ideology highlights the importance of nurturing not only knowledge but also understanding, values, abilities, attitudes, and the overall interest of students in achieving task mastery (Deakin & Joldersma, 2007; Redma & Wiek, 2021)

In 2017, Kenya embarked on a significant educational paradigm shift by introducing the Competency-Based Curriculum, replacing the previous 8-4-4 system of education (Republic of Kenya, 2017). This learner-centred approach, designed by the Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (K.I.C.D.), spans different education levels, including early years, middle school, senior school, and tertiary education (Basic Curriculum Reform Framework, 2016; Fomiškina et al., 2021;

Ruth, 2019; Kaviti, 2018; K.I.C.D., 2016). It aims to provide students with a holistic education that not only prepares them for higher education and the labour market but also fosters their creativity and critical thinking skills.

Under the competency-based curriculum, learners are encouraged to take ownership of their learning, guided by teachers who facilitate their development in specific study areas. Learning objectives are clearly defined, making them more manageable and enabling assessment through various means, such as assignments and projects.

This paper examines the impact of the educational paradigm shift, specifically the Competency-Based Curriculum, on the Kenyan education system. By investigating its implementation, challenges, and outcomes, the paper aims to shed light on the effectiveness and implications of this new approach. The findings of this study can contribute to educational policy formulation and instructional practices and, ultimately, enhance student outcomes in Kenya.

Importance

The competency-based curriculum represents a shift towards a learner-centred approach, in contrast to the previous teacher-centred mode of education. It places a greater emphasis on practicality and the development of competencies that enhance students' success in their careers (East African Community, 2014). This forward-looking curriculum aims to provide a futuristic form of education by focusing on the cultivation of essential skills such as effective communication, critical thinking, and problem-solving. These skills are fundamental for students to navigate their lives and adapt to the rapidly changing environment (Dede, 2010).

Background Information

Kenya has gradually transitioned through different education systems since its independence in 1963. Initially, the British introduced the 7-4-2-3 system, consisting of seven years of primary education, four years of junior secondary education, two years of upper secondary education, and a minimum of three years of university education (Wanjohi, 2011; Lelei & Weidman, 2012; Amunga, Were, & Ashioya, 2020). However, this system failed to achieve its intended objectives of providing skilled personnel capable of meeting workforce demands and facilitating career development (Wanjohi, 2011). Consequently, the 8-4-4 education system replaced it in 1985, comprising eight years of primary school, four years of secondary school, and a minimum of four years of university education.

Traditionally, the Kenyan education system, particularly under the 8-4-4 system, adopted a teacher-centred approach with an emphasis on rote memorization and a content-driven curriculum (Luan & Bakar, 2008). While this approach provided a foundation of knowledge, it faced criticism for its limited focus on real-world applications, critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving abilities.

Throughout the years, various education reforms have been implemented in an attempt to address the challenges of unemployment and the relevance of education in Kenya (Republic of Kenya, 1964; Sifuna & Obonyo, 2019). Several commissions were established, including the Ominde Commission (1964), Bessey Commission (1972), Gachathi Commission (1976), Mackay Commission (1981), Kamunge Commission (1988), and Koech Commission (1999), all aiming to reform the education system. However, these reforms faced their challenges, and further revisions were deemed necessary.

In early January 2011, the Kenyan government recognized the need to revisit, review, and reform the education system to meet international standards and provide learners with the necessary skills for the job market (Sifuna & Obonyo, 2019). The Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (K.I.C.D.) was thus tasked with this responsibility. Their report emphasized the importance of equipping learners with competence in various areas, facilitating early career development, and focusing on vocational education and practical subjects.

As a result, the competency-based curriculum (C.B.C.) was introduced, featuring seven key competencies for learners: creativity and imagination, patriotism, I.C.T. literacy, communication and collaboration, critical thinking and problem-solving, learning to learn, and self-actualization. The implementation of the C.B.C. involved the development of frameworks and materials, teacher training, and a phased rollout starting in January 2017 (Republic of Kenya, 2012). Despite challenges encountered during the pilot study and implementation process, the Kenyan government remained

committed to fully implementing the competency-based curriculum by January 2019 to address the embedded challenges within the education system (Republic of Kenya, 2012). Therefore, understanding the historical context and the paradigm shift represented by the Competency-Based Curriculum is important for examining its impact on the Kenyan education system by adopting a learner-centred approach and emphasizing practical skills development, as the C.B.C. aims to better prepare students for the demands of the 21st-century world.

Problem statement

The Kenyan education system has faced challenges in equipping students with the necessary skills and competencies required for success in the 21st century. The previous education system, the 8-4-4 system, had limitations in its teacher-centred approach and its ability to foster practical skills and critical thinking among students. In response to these challenges, a new educational paradigm shift was implemented in Kenya known as the Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.). However, there is a need to assess the impact of this educational reform on the Kenyan education system, including its effectiveness in promoting learner-centred approaches, enhancing practical skills development, and addressing the demands of the 21st-century workforce. Therefore, this study aims to examine the impact of the C.B.C. on the Kenyan education system and provide insights for educational policy formulation and instructional practices.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of the educational paradigm shift, specifically the Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.), on the Kenyan education system. The study aims to investigate the implementation of the C.B.C., identify the challenges encountered during its adoption, and analyze the outcomes and effectiveness of this new approach in shaping the educational landscape in Kenya.

By conducting this research, we seek to shed light on the implications of the C.B.C. on teaching and learning practices, curriculum development, and student outcomes. The findings of this study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on educational reform and policy formulation, providing insights into the strengths, limitations, and potential areas of improvement in the C.B.C. implementation.

Research objectives

1. To examine the key features and principles of the Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.) implemented in the Kenyan education system.
2. To identify the challenges encountered during the implementation of the C.B.C. in Kenya.
3. To evaluate the impact of the C.B.C. on student outcomes, including academic performance and the acquisition of key competencies.

Research questions

1. What are the fundamental principles underlying the C.B.C. in the Kenyan education system?
2. What were the main obstacles and difficulties faced during the adoption of the C.B.C.?
3. How did various stakeholders, such as teachers, students, and policymakers, perceive and respond to these challenges?
4. What changes have been observed in students' academic achievements and learning outcomes under the C.B.C.?

Significance of the study

The significance of studying the impact of the educational paradigm shift, specifically the Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.), on the Kenyan education system is multifaceted. By examining this shift, the study can contribute to various aspects of education, including policy formulation, teaching practices, and student outcomes. The findings can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the curriculum reform and inform future decision-making processes. Policymakers can use the research findings to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the C.B.C., make necessary adjustments, and improve the overall quality of education in Kenya. This can lead to the development of evidence-based policies that align with the needs of students and the evolving demands of the 21st century.

The study's findings also can have a direct impact on student outcomes. By evaluating the impact of the C.B.C., the research can provide insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the curriculum in terms of preparing students for

higher education, the labour market, and overall success in their future careers. The findings can guide efforts to optimize the curriculum's ability to cultivate the desired competencies and skills required in the 21st century. Ultimately, this can contribute to improved student performance, increased employability, and better alignment of education with the needs of society.

The study also offers guidance for teaching practices in the sense that educators can gain a deeper understanding of how the C.B.C. influences instructional approaches, assessment methods, and classroom dynamics. The findings can inform teachers on how to effectively implement the curriculum, promote learner-centred approaches, and foster the development of practical skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities among students. This can result in more engaging and effective teaching practices that enhance student-learning outcomes.

Literature Review

Overview of Competence-Based Education

Competency-based education (C.B.E.) is an educational approach that has gained significant attention in recent years. Scholars and researchers have explored various aspects of C.B.E., including its theoretical foundations, implementation strategies, and impacts on student learning outcomes. (Wesselink et al.,2007) Their research focused on competence-based vocational education and training (V.E.T.), which provides insight into the theoretical foundations of competence-based learning and the principles that underpin it. In their argumentation, they state that key elements of competency-based education exist, which are the integration of knowledge, skills, and attitudes, as well as the emphasis on real-life and authentic learning experiences. These elements are important as they highlight the importance of aligning the curriculum with occupational standards and industry requirements to ensure the relevance and effectiveness of Competency-based education programs.

These theoretical foundations of C.B.E. also emphasize the learner-centred approach, which is a shift from a traditional content-based curriculum to one focused on the development of competencies. These competencies, thus, lead to the alignment with the demands of the 21st-century workforce, which requires individuals to possess not only subject knowledge but also a range of skills and abilities to succeed in diverse professional settings (Chakraborty & Nafukho, 2016). While there are various obstacles to the successful implementation of Competency-Based Education (C.B.E.) across all levels, such as the requirement for qualified teachers, suitable assessment techniques, curriculum redesign, educator training, alignment with industry standards, and strong collaboration between educational institutions and industry stakeholders, it is crucial to prioritize institutional dedication, stakeholder involvement, and effective approaches to curriculum design and assessment. Additionally, fostering learner autonomy, self-directed learning, and the cultivation of transferable competencies are essential elements in achieving successful implementation of C.B.E. (Brown & Trotter, 2017)

There exists the importance of aligning education and training with the needs of the workforce through the educational shift, as the traditional educational approaches may not adequately equip individuals with the skills and competencies required in today's rapidly changing and complex work environments (Kinshuk et al., 2016). On the other hand, competency-based education and training offer a more tailored and practical approach to learning through the integrated development of knowledge, skills, and attitudes required for effective performance in a specific profession or occupation, aiming to develop specific competencies that directly relate to job roles and tasks through the competencies acquired by the learners (Mulder, 2016). Furthermore, he discussed the potential impact of C.B.E. on student learning outcomes, such as enhancement of student's mastery of specific competencies and their ability to apply knowledge in a real-world context, improvement of students' engagement, motivation, and the development of transferable skills that meet the workforce market.

Educational Paradigm Shift and the Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.)

In recent years, there has been a significant paradigm shift in the field of education, moving away from traditional approaches to more learner-centred and outcomes-based models. One notable development is the emergence of

Competency-Based Education (C.B.E.), which focuses on the acquisition of specific skills and competencies rather than solely emphasizing content knowledge (Gruppen., et al., 2016). The Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.) is an educational framework that embodies this paradigm shift. It has been implemented in various countries, including Kenya, with the aim of equipping students with the skills, knowledge, and attitudes needed to thrive in the 21st century. The C.B.C. places a strong emphasis on the development of key competencies, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, collaboration, creativity, and digital literacy (Gulled, 2023).

The implementation of the C.B.C. involves a departure from the traditional subject-based curriculum towards an integrated and interdisciplinary approach. It seeks to create meaningful connections between different subject areas and real-world contexts, promoting holistic learning experiences for students. The C.B.C. also encourages active student engagement, self-directed learning, and continuous assessment to monitor students' progress and provide targeted support. These experiences are facilitated by the development of competencies, such as critical thinking, communication, and problem-solving, that are relevant and facilitate the learners to adapt to the changing demands of the job market (N.A.C.E., 2020)

Studies on the impact of educational shifts

There are various impacts of educational change, including changes in educational systems, approaches, and policies on various aspects of teaching and learning. These studies investigate the outcomes, challenges, and benefits associated with educational shifts, such as curriculum changes, pedagogical reforms, and the adoption of new technologies in the classroom environment. Hargreaves and Fullan (2012) emphasize educational reform and its impact on the teaching and learning process, whereby they put more emphasis on the significance of developing professional capital as a crucial element in supporting effective curriculum changes and educational shifts. This concept of professional capital comprises three key components: human capital, social capital, and decisional capital. Human capital, in this case, refers to the knowledge, skills, and expertise possessed by educators.

In contrast, social capital emphasizes the importance of collaborative relationships and networks among teachers and other stakeholders. In contrast, decisional capital focuses on the capacity of educators to make informed decisions and exercise professional judgment. By nurturing these components, the educational systems can enhance the quality of teaching and learning, promote innovation, and drive successful educational reform.

The structural and cultural aspects of educational change exist in the sense that every successful educational shift requires not only policy adjustments and new curriculum frameworks but also a deep transformation in the culture and practices within educational institutions (Fullan, 2016). According to Fullan, creating a positive and collaborative culture that fosters trust, shared vision, and collective efficacy is crucial for sustainable change. In addition, the critical role of leadership is also important, as there is a need for distributed leadership, where school administrators, teachers, and other stakeholders collaborate and take shared responsibility for implementing change. Instructional practices and pedagogy are also whereby student-centred and inquiry-based learning is prioritized, which in turn improves the competence of the learners.

Sahlberg (2015), in his studies, puts forward some of the foreseen outcomes brought about by the educational shift in the Finnish curriculum. He argues that the educational shift towards a student-centred approach in Finland has yielded significant positive impacts. Finland ranked among the top-performing countries globally, with high academic achievement and reduced achievement gaps. The emphasis on critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity has produced engaged and motivated learners who develop a broader set of competencies. The student-centred approach has also fostered positive well-being among students, promoting a holistic approach to education. Additionally, it has elevated teacher professionalism and job satisfaction, resulting in an effective teaching-learning process.

Levin (2010), in his studies on educational reform and instructional change in Alberta, several challenges and successes emerge. The implementation of curriculum changes poses challenges, such as the need for comprehensive teacher professional development to align best instructional practices with the new curriculum in place. Ongoing support and

training which are essential for teachers to adapt to the new curriculum. Balancing standardized assessments and student-centred approaches presents another challenge, as finding the right equilibrium between accountability and meaningful learning experiences is complex. However, the study also highlights successes in instructional change. They include teacher collaboration and the sharing of best practices to contribute to improved instructional quality. Creating supportive professional learning communities fosters collaboration and idea exchange among educators. Additionally, when accompanied by effective professional development initiatives, curriculum changes have the potential to enhance student achievement.

Gaps or limitations in the existing literature and the need for further research

These gaps highlight the need for further research in the field of educational shifts and curriculum changes. They include a focus on the short-term outcomes of the changes made rather than examining the long-term impact of these changes. This is associated with the need to explore the sustained effects of educational shifts and curriculum changes on student achievement, engagement, and success beyond immediate implementation periods. Beyond academic achievement, it is also important to explore the impact of curriculum changes on broader student outcomes by examining the effects on critical thinking skills, creativity, social-emotional development, and lifelong learning competencies. There also exists an overemphasis on the influence of contextual factors on the implementation and effectiveness of curriculum changes rather than delving deeper into how factors such as school culture, community support, resource availability, and the policy environment shape the implementation process and outcomes.

Teacher experience, who are the facilitators of the implementation of the curriculum change, has yet to be explored in the literature. Therefore, there is a need for additional research so as to understand how teachers perceive and navigate curriculum changes, the challenges they face, and the types of professional development that effectively support their implementation efforts. Furthermore, the literature on educational shifts and curriculum changes needs a comprehensive examination of the impact on marginalized and disadvantaged student populations. Therefore, research is needed to investigate how these changes affect students with diverse backgrounds, abilities, and needs and whether they exacerbate or alleviate existing inequities in educational outcomes. Another aspect of consideration is that effective stakeholder engagement and collaboration in the process of educational shifts and curriculum changes is limited. More studies are needed to understand how to effectively involve various stakeholders, such as parents, government, community members, and policymakers, in decision-making and implementation processes.

Sustainability and scalability are also an aspect that has yet to be delved into vividly, as more focus has shifted to small-scale pilot projects or specific contexts, limiting our understanding of how curriculum changes can be effectively implemented and sustained across different educational settings and at a larger scale. Additionally, while various models and strategies for curriculum implementation have been discussed in the literature, further research is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of these approaches in different contexts. Comparative studies that examine the outcomes of different implementation strategies can provide valuable insights into best practices and effective approaches.

Theoretical framework

Implementation Science theory

Implementation science emerged as a distinct discipline in the 1990s, drawing upon various fields such as psychology, organizational behaviour, public health, and education. Scholars and researchers such as Carl E. Taylor, Brian S. Mittman, David Chambers, Gregory A. Aarons, and Enola K. Proctor, among many others from different disciplines, have contributed to the development of Implementation Science by examining the processes, strategies, and factors that influence the successful implementation of interventions and changes in various domains, including education (Stokols et al., 2008).

Implementation Science is a theory that provides a systematic and evidence-based approach to effectively implementing and sustaining educational interventions or changes, such as curriculum reforms. It focuses on bridging the gap between research and practice by identifying the best strategies for successfully implementing and integrating new

initiatives into educational settings. One key aspect of Implementation Science is the emphasis on understanding and addressing the contextual factors that can influence the success of implementation (Cook & Odom, 2013). This includes factors such as the organizational culture, leadership support, available resources, teacher readiness, and the social and political climate. By considering these contextual factors, educators can develop tailored implementation plans that are sensitive to the specific needs and realities of their educational setting.

Evidence-based practices and strategies to guide the implementation process are also emphasized as they involve drawing upon research and existing knowledge about effective implementation methods, such as the use of implementation frameworks, fidelity monitoring, and continuous evaluation and improvement. By employing evidence-based practices, educators can increase the likelihood of successful implementation and improve the outcomes of curriculum changes (Nutley et al., 2003). On the other hand, collaboration and engagement among stakeholders such as teachers, administrators, students, parents, and other relevant stakeholders in decision-making, planning, and implementation activities throughout the implementation process is necessary. This is because collaborative efforts promote a sense of ownership and shared responsibility, increasing the likelihood of successful adoption and sustainability of the curriculum changes. Another vital component of Implementation Science is the consideration of implementation outcomes and evaluation (Bland et al., 2000). This involves monitoring the progress of implementation, assessing fidelity to the intended curriculum changes, and evaluating the impact on student learning outcomes. By systematically evaluating the implementation process, educators can identify areas of improvement, make necessary adjustments, and ensure continuous quality improvement.

Research Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods research approach to investigate the educational shifts and curriculum changes. This involved a combination of qualitative and quantitative data collection methods, sample selection, and analysis techniques.

Data Collection Methods

For qualitative data collection, a questionnaire and focus group discussions were conducted with key stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, students, parents, and policymakers. These questionnaires and discussions aimed to gather rich and detailed insights into their perspectives, experiences, and perceptions regarding educational shifts and curriculum changes. Open-ended questions were used to encourage participants to share their thoughts and provide nuanced responses.

In addition to qualitative data, quantitative data were collected through surveys administered to a larger sample of participants. The surveys included structured questions and rating scales to gather quantitative information on participants' attitudes, opinions, and experiences related to the implementation of curriculum changes. The surveys were distributed electronically.

Sample Selection

The selection of the sample for this study followed a purposive sampling strategy. Participants were selected based on their relevance to the research topic and their involvement in educational shifts and curriculum changes. Teachers, administrators, students, parents, and policymakers from diverse educational settings, such as different schools or counties, were included to capture a wide range of perspectives and experiences. The sample size was determined based on the principle of data saturation, where new information and insights ceased to emerge from the data.

Analysis Techniques

Qualitative data analysis involved a thematic analysis approach. The recorded questionnaire and focus group discussions were transcribed and analyzed using qualitative data analysis S.P.S.S. version 26 software. The data was coded, categorized, and clustered into themes and subthemes to identify patterns, recurring ideas, and key findings. The analysis process involved iterative and systematic reviews of the data to ensure the reliability and validity of the identified themes.

Quantitative data analysis included descriptive statistics, such as frequencies and percentages, to summarize the survey responses. Statistical analysis techniques, such as correlations or regression analysis, were employed to examine relationships between variables and identify any significant associations or patterns in the data. The quantitative data analysis was performed using statistical software (S.P.S.S.) as well to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings.

Research findings and discussion

The impacts of education paradigm shift

The paradigm shift in the education system in Kenya is important in various aspects towards the progression of a country's effort to revitalize itself economically as well as socially to ensure successful outcomes.

		Per Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Teacher training and professional development	0	13	13.8	13.8
	Teacher training and professional development	81	86.2	86.2
	Total	94	100.0	100.0
Change of teaching methods	0	28	29.8	29.8
	Change of teaching methods	66	70.2	70.2
	Total	94	100.0	100.0
Change of assessment method	0	30	31.9	31.9
	Change of assessment method	64	68.1	68.1
	Total	94	100.0	100.0
Infrastructure and resources development	0	25	26.6	26.6
	Infrastructure and resources development	69	73.4	73.4
	Total	94	100.0	100.0

Table 1: Stakeholders' adoption of C.B.C.

This reform provides insight into what to improve. Thus, the competency-based curriculum in this paper has provided directions on key areas to be studied and how it should be achieved through a pedagogy of selecting specific study areas as well as the various teaching strategies to be put in place.

Table 1 reveals several significant findings. First, a majority of participants (86.2%) emphasized the importance of teacher training and professional development as a critical aspect of successful curriculum implementation. This finding underscores the recognition among educators of the need for ongoing support and training to equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge to implement new curriculum initiatives effectively. A substantial proportion of respondents (70.2%) acknowledged the need for a change in teaching methods. This highlights educators' awareness of the importance of adapting instructional strategies to align with the goals and requirements of the revised curriculum. The recognition of the need for innovative and student-centred teaching approaches signifies a shift towards creating engaging and interactive learning environments that cater to diverse student needs.

Additionally, the findings indicate that participants (68.1%) recognized the importance of modifying assessment methods to align with the objectives and expectations of the new curriculum. This demonstrates an understanding among educators of the need for authentic and formative assessment practices that promote continuous feedback, self-reflection, and the development of higher-order thinking skills.

Challenges in implementing the C.B.C

The Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.) has been introduced as an innovative approach to education, aiming to enhance student-learning outcomes by focusing on the development of essential competencies. However, the successful implementation of the C.B.C. has its challenges. This study investigates the challenges faced by educators and stakeholders in implementing the C.B.C. in Kenya. By examining the findings, this research provides insights into the key challenges encountered during the implementation process and their implications for effective curriculum delivery. Based on the findings, as shown in Table 2, one prominent challenge reported by the participants is resistance to change. Approximately 63.8% of the respondents acknowledged resistance to the C.B.C. implementation. This resistance could stem from various factors, such as reluctance to adopt new teaching and assessment approaches, concerns about increased workload, or scepticism about the effectiveness of the new curriculum. Addressing this challenge requires targeted efforts to engage stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, and parents, in understanding the rationale and benefits of the C.B.C., as well as providing support and training to facilitate a smooth transition.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Resistance to change	0	34	36.2	36.2	36.2
	Resistance to change	60	63.8	63.8	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Limited resources	0	9	9.6	9.6	9.6
	Limited resources	85	90.4	90.4	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Student motivation	0	55	58.5	58.5	58.5
	Student motivation	39	41.5	41.5	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Curriculum development	0	38	40.4	40.4	40.4
	Curriculum development	56	59.6	59.6	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Assessment approach	0	51	54.3	54.3	54.3
	Assessment approach	43	45.7	45.7	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Teacher training	0	37	39.4	39.4	39.4
	Teacher training	57	60.6	60.6	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Inadequate monitoring and evaluation	0	46	48.9	48.9	48.9
	Inadequate monitoring and evaluation	48	51.1	51.1	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Lack of public participation	0	47	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Lack of public participation	47	50.0	50.0	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Challenges in implementing C.B.C.

Another challenge is the limited resources, with 90.4% of participants identifying this issue. There need to be more resources to ensure the availability of textbooks, teaching materials, technological infrastructure, and other essential resources, which can hinder the effective implementation of the C.B.C. Adequate investment in resources is crucial to ensure that educators have the necessary tools and materials to deliver the curriculum effectively and provide students with meaningful learning experiences.

Student motivation was identified as a challenge by 41.5% of participants. Implementing a competency-based approach may require students to take more ownership of their learning and actively engage in the curriculum. Overcoming student apathy or disengagement requires strategies to enhance intrinsic motivation, create relevant and engaging learning experiences, and foster a supportive learning environment.

Other challenges reported include curriculum development (59.6%), assessment approach (45.7%), teacher training (60.6%), inadequate monitoring and evaluation (51.1%), and lack of public participation (50%).

These findings underscore the need for comprehensive curriculum development processes, appropriate assessment methods aligned with the C.B.C., targeted teacher training and professional development, robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, and meaningful engagement of the public in the implementation process.

Addressing the challenges in implementing C.B.C

The implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.) presents various challenges that need to be effectively addressed to ensure its successful adoption and integration into educational systems.

To gain insights into potential solutions, an open questionnaire was conducted to gather opinions on how to address the challenges associated with implementing the C.B.C. This study aimed to explore the perspectives and suggestions of educators, administrators, policymakers, and other stakeholders on strategies and measures that can be implemented to overcome the identified obstacles, as shown in Table 3.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Teacher training	0	72	76.6	76.6	76.6
	Teacher training	22	23.4	23.4	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Educating the public on the importance of C.B.C.	0	72	76.6	76.6	76.6
	Educating the public on the importance of C.B.C.	22	23.4	23.4	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Adequate financing by the government	0	25	26.6	26.6	26.6
	Adequate financing by the government	69	73.4	73.4	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Stakeholder involvement	0	84	89.4	89.4	89.4
	Stakeholder involvement	10	10.6	10.6	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	
Students' motivation	0	93	98.9	98.9	98.9
	Students' motivation	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Addressing challenges associated with C.B.C.

The findings in Table 3 reveal several key strategies and recommendations provided by the participants to address the challenges associated with implementing the Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.). These strategies include teacher training, which emerged as a prominent suggestion, with 76.6% of participants emphasizing the need for comprehensive training programs. Participants highlighted the importance of equipping teachers with the necessary knowledge and skills to implement the C.B.C. well. Professional development initiatives that focus on pedagogical approaches, curriculum design, and assessment methods specific to the C.B.C. were identified as crucial in building teacher capacity and confidence. Another significant recommendation was educating the public on the importance of C.B.C., as voiced by 76.6% of participants. Participants recognized the need to generate awareness and understanding among parents, community members, and other stakeholders about the goals and benefits of the C.B.C. By fostering a supportive environment and addressing misconceptions, public education campaigns can help create a shared understanding and commitment to the successful implementation of the Competence-based curriculum (C.B.C.)

Adequate financing by the government was identified by 73.4% of participants as a crucial factor in addressing the challenges associated with the C.B.C. Participants highlighted the need for sufficient resources to support curriculum development, infrastructure improvements, and the provision of instructional materials aligned with the C.B.C. Adequate funding can ensure the availability of necessary resources that is crucial for the implementation and support the curriculum shift process. Stakeholder involvement was also emphasized by 89.4% of participants as a vital strategy. Whereby, engaging various stakeholders, including teachers, parents, students, administrators, policymakers, and community members, can foster collaboration and shared responsibility in implementing the C.B.C. Participants highlighted the importance of creating platforms for dialogue, involving stakeholders in decision-making processes and actively seeking their feedback and perspectives.

Student motivation was also recognized as an essential aspect, with 98.9% of participants emphasizing the need to address this challenge. Participants suggested incorporating engaging teaching methodologies, project-based learning, and creating meaningful connections between curriculum content and real-life contexts to enhance student motivation and active participation in the C.B.C.

Impact of C.B.C. based on competencies

The competency-based curriculum (C.B.C.) is based on several key principles. These principles include students progressing based on demonstrated mastery of skills, using assessment as a means to determine skill mastery, and fostering competencies that can be applied and transferred across different contexts. C.B.C. also emphasizes learning outcomes that focus on the application and creation of knowledge, as well as the development of students' dispositions. This is attributed to the fact that C.B.C. allows for individualized learning, ensuring that each student receives adequate time to acquire and demonstrate their skills based on their unique learning capabilities. This learner-centred approach of the C.B.C. therefore, marks a departure from the traditional teacher-centred approach that prioritized examinations. By aligning with these principles, the C.B.C. has the potential to enhance students' outcomes and promote a more comprehensive and holistic learning experience. As shown in Table 4, the competency of patriotism was viewed as important or more important by a majority of respondents, with 76.4% considering it important or very important. This suggests that C.B.C. has been effective in instilling a sense of patriotism among students, emphasizing the importance of national identity and values.

Communication skills and collaboration were highlighted as important competencies by the respondents. A significant portion (72.3%) considered these skills to be more important or very important, indicating that C.B.C. has contributed positively to the development of effective communication and collaboration skills among students. This finding aligns with the broader goals of C.B.C., which emphasize the importance of fostering interpersonal skills and teamwork.

Imagination and creativity were perceived as vital competencies by the majority of respondents, with 61.7% considering them more important or very important. This suggests that C.B.C. has played a role in nurturing students' imaginative thinking and creative abilities, fostering innovation and originality. On the other hand, self-actualization, which

encompasses self-discovery, personal growth, and fulfilment, was regarded as an important or more important competency by a majority of respondents (68.1%). This finding indicates that C.B.C. has had a positive impact on enabling students to explore their potential, set goals, and strive for personal development and fulfilment.

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Patriotism	Not important at all	4	4.3	4.3
	Less important	2	2.1	6.4
	Important	50	53.2	59.6
	More important	22	23.4	83.0
	Very important	16	17.0	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Communication skills and collaboration	Not important at all	4	4.3	4.3
	Less important	1	1.1	5.3
	Important	37	39.4	44.7
	More important	26	27.7	72.3
	Very important	26	27.7	100.0
Total	94	100.0		
Imagination and creativity	Not important at all	2	2.1	2.1
	Less important	2	2.1	4.3
	Important	25	26.6	30.9
	More important	29	30.9	61.7
	Very important	36	38.3	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Self-actualization	Not important at all	2	2.1	2.1
	Important	34	36.2	38.3
	More important	28	29.8	68.1
	Very important	30	31.9	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Learning as a means to an end	Not important at all	4	4.3	4.3
	Less important	3	3.2	7.4
	Important	34	36.2	43.6
	More important	23	24.5	68.1
	Very important	30	31.9	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
ICT literacy	Not important at all	2	2.1	2.1
	Less important	1	1.1	3.2
	Important	23	24.5	27.7
	More important	33	35.1	62.8
	Very important	35	37.2	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	

Table 4: Impact of C.B.C. based on Competencies.

In regards to the competency of learning as a means to an end, respondents' opinions were divided. While 68.1% considered it important or more important, a significant proportion (7.4%) viewed it as less important. This suggests

the existence of differing perspectives on the purpose and value of learning, with some emphasizing the instrumental nature of education while others recognize its intrinsic worth.

Lastly, I.C.T. literacy was perceived as significant, with 62.8% of respondents considering it more important or very important. This finding highlights the role of C.B.C. in equipping students with essential digital literacy skills, enabling them to navigate and utilize information and communication technologies effectively.

Impact of C.B.C. implementation on teaching and assessment methods

The implementation of competence-based curriculum (C.B.C.) in schools has had the aim of transforming teaching and learning approaches to better equip students with the necessary competencies for success in the 21st century. One key aspect of evaluating the effectiveness of the C.B.C. is examining its impact on teaching and assessment methods. This study investigates the changes observed in teaching and assessment practices since the implementation of the C.B.C., shedding light on the extent to which the curriculum has influenced instructional approaches.

		Valid Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Shift to a learner-centered approach	0	10	10.6	10.6
	Shift from teacher-centred approach to a learner-centred approach	84	89.4	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Emphasis on practicality	0	24	25.5	25.5
	Emphasis on practicality	70	74.5	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Hands-on learning and problem solving	0	37	39.4	39.4
	Hands-on learning and problem solving	57	60.6	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Use of performance-based assessment	0	27	28.7	28.7
	Use of performance-based assessment through projects and presentation	67	71.3	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Use of continuous evaluation and formative assessment	0	40	42.6	42.6
	Use of continuous evaluation and formative assessment	54	57.4	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
focus on students' competencies in applying the acquired knowledge rather than the ability to recall information	0	33	35.1	35.1
	focus on students' competencies in applying the acquired knowledge rather than the ability to recall information	61	64.9	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	

Table 5: Impact of C.B.C. implementation on teaching and assessment methods.

As shown in Table 5 above, the majority of respondents (89.4%) reported a clear shift from a traditional teacher-centred approach to a learner-centred approach. This finding suggests that educators have recognized the importance of engaging students actively in the learning process, fostering their autonomy, and encouraging critical thinking skills. The transition to a learner-centred approach indicates a pedagogical shift that prioritizes student engagement, participation, and self-directed learning. Another prominent finding is the emphasis on practicality in teaching methods, as reported by 74.5% of respondents. This indicates a departure from purely theoretical instruction to incorporating practical elements in the classroom. Practicality in teaching methods implies a focus on the real-world application of

knowledge and skills, allowing students to see the relevance and value of what they are learning. This approach fosters a deeper understanding of concepts and enhances students' ability to transfer their learning to practical situations.

The results also highlight the importance of hands-on learning and problem-solving in C.B.C. implementation. A significant majority of respondents (60.6%) reported the incorporation of hands-on learning and problem-solving activities in the classroom. This finding suggests a shift towards more experiential and interactive learning experiences that enable students to explore and solve real-world problems actively. Such an approach not only enhances students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills but also promotes their creativity and innovation.

In terms of assessment methods, the findings indicate a move towards performance-based assessment. A substantial number of respondents (71.3%) reported the use of performance-based assessments, such as projects and presentations. This shift aligns with the competency-based approach, as it focuses on evaluating students' ability to apply their knowledge and skills in practical contexts. Performance-based assessments provide a more authentic and holistic measure of students' competencies, going beyond rote memorization and recall of information.

The incorporation of continuous evaluation and formative assessment practices was another impact of C.B.C., whereby approximately 57.4% of respondents reported the use of continuous evaluation and formative assessment methods. This approach emphasizes ongoing feedback and assessment throughout the learning process, enabling teachers to monitor students' progress and provide timely support. Continuous evaluation and formative assessment strategies support personalized learning and help students identify areas for improvement, leading to enhanced learning outcomes.

Finally, the findings indicate a shift towards a focus on students' competencies in applying acquired knowledge rather than solely assessing their ability to recall information. This shift was reported by 64.9% of respondents. By emphasizing competencies, the C.B.C. encourages students to develop practical skills, critical thinking abilities, and the capacity to apply their knowledge in meaningful ways. This moves away from rote memorization towards a competency-based approach reflects a broader educational shift towards fostering students' overall development and readiness for real-world challenges.

Impact of C.B.C. implementation on the development and use of educational resources and materials

The competency-based curriculum (C.B.C.) implementation in Kenya has brought about significant changes in the education system, including the development and use of educational resources and materials. The findings provide valuable insights into the perceptions and preferences of educators and stakeholders regarding the integration of technology, simulation materials, case studies, and interactive learning activities within the C.B.C. framework. Understanding these impacts is important for ensuring that educational resources and materials align with the competencies and learning outcomes as emphasized by the C.B.C., ultimately enhancing the teaching and learning experience for both students and educators.

As shown in Table 6, the majority of respondents acknowledge the significance of technology in education, with 80.9% emphasizing the importance of online and digital resources. This reflects a recognition of the potential of technology to enhance teaching and learning experiences within the C.B.C. framework.

Furthermore, the use of simulation materials emerged as another important aspect, with 68.1% of respondents considering it more important or very important. This indicates an understanding of the value of incorporating realistic and practical learning experiences that align with the competency-based nature of the C.B.C. In addition, a majority of respondents also regarded case study materials as important, with 70.2% expressing their significance. The inclusion of case studies allows students to analyze real-world situations, fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are integral to the competency-based approach.

Lastly, the findings highlight the importance of interactive learning activities, as indicated by 63.8% of respondents. This emphasizes the value of engaging students through group discussions, cooperative learning, and hands-on activities, which promote a deeper understanding and application of acquired knowledge.

		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Use of technology in education (Online and digital resources)	Not important at all	2	2.1	2.1
	Less important	3	3.2	5.3
	Important	41	43.6	48.9
	More important	30	31.9	80.9
	Very important	18	19.1	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Use of simulation materials	Not important at all	2	2.1	2.1
	Less important	3	3.2	5.3
	Important	33	35.1	40.4
	More important	26	27.7	68.1
	Very important	30	31.9	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Use of case study materials	It is not important at all	3	3.2	3.2
	Less important	4	4.3	7.4
	Important	31	33.0	40.4
	More important	28	29.8	70.2
	Very important	28	29.8	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Use of interactive learning activities	Not important at all	2	2.1	2.1
	Less important	1	1.1	3.2
	Important	27	28.7	31.9
	More important	30	31.9	63.8
	Very important	34	36.2	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	

Table 6: Impact of C.B.C. implementation on the development and use of educational resources and materials.

Impact of C.B.C. implementation on students' learning outcomes

The implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum (C.B.C.) in Kenya has brought about significant changes in students' learning outcomes. The findings from the study on the impact of C.B.C. implementation highlight several key areas where the curriculum has positively influenced students' development and achievements. As shown in Table 7, the key areas include improved communication skills, which were considered important or more important by a significant majority of respondents, with 75.5% expressing their significance. This suggests that the C.B.C. has had a positive influence on enhancing students' communication abilities, emphasizing its importance in preparing them for effective interaction and expression of ideas.

Furthermore, the discovery of talents was also perceived as important or more important by 60.6% of respondents. This indicates that the C.B.C. implementation has created an environment that encourages students to explore and uncover their unique abilities and talents, allowing for holistic development beyond academic achievements.

		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Improved communication skills	Not important at all	1	1.1	1.1
	Less important	2	2.1	3.2
	Important	35	37.2	40.4
	More important	33	35.1	75.5
	Very important	23	24.5	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Discovering talents	Not important at all	1	1.1	1.1
	Less important	2	2.1	3.2
	Important	24	25.5	28.7
	More important	30	31.9	60.6
	Very important	37	39.4	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	
Increased opportunities for children	Not important at all	2	2.1	2.1
	Less important	2	2.1	4.3
	Important	31	33.0	37.2
	More important	37	39.4	76.6
	Very important	22	23.4	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	100.0
Digital literacy	Not important at all	1	1.1	1.1
	Important	22	23.4	24.5
	More important	47	50.0	74.5
	Very important	24	25.5	100.0
Creativity and imagination	Total	94	100.0	
	It is not important at all	1	1.1	1.1
	Less important	1	1.1	2.1
	Important	20	21.3	23.4
	More important	36	38.3	61.7
	Very important	36	38.3	100.0
Total	94	100.0		

Table 7: Impact of C.B.C. implementation on students' learning outcomes.

A considerable number of respondents (76.6%) highlighted the increased opportunities for children resulting from C.B.C. implementation. This finding suggests that the competency-based approach has opened up avenues for students to access a broader range of educational opportunities, potentially leading to improved academic and personal growth. In terms of digital literacy, a majority of respondents (74.5%) considered it more important or very important. This highlights the recognition of the importance of equipping students with digital skills necessary for their future success in a technology-driven world. Lastly, creativity and imagination were also regarded as significant by 61.7% of respondents. This indicates that the C.B.C. has nurtured and encouraged students' creative thinking and imagination, fostering their ability to approach problems innovatively and think outside the box.

Conclusion

The newly implemented competency-based curriculum has already had some of the impacts that have been felt by the stakeholders through the learners' performance in the completion of various tasks, as they have different innovative skills to complete various tasks assigned to them. Early identification of talents has been noticed through the facilitators'

interaction with the learners, as they tend to concentrate more on their field of interest, thereby narrowing down the subject areas according to different learners' capabilities. The generally intended impacts of the competency-based curriculum seem to be taking shape as it aims to solve the challenges faced by the country that the 8-4-4 education system failed to solve. Therefore, it is just a matter of time before the objectives set out by the curriculum are actualized, and the stakeholders should look at the new curriculum with seriousness, as it will have some impact. Reference to other developed nations, including the U.S.A., that have competence-based curricula, which have failed to meet the poor performance by the learners, should be examined carefully so as to note which aspects they fail to address during their implementation process and the running process so as to have an insight on what are the potential threats that the new curriculum can pose and how to solve them as well.

Recommendation

Various recommendations are paramount to ensure that the competence-based curriculum gets to be implemented fully and thus adapted to the Kenyan education system. They include;

- I. Fully subsidizing the education system, specifically, the early year education and the Middle school education, as this is the core basis of the curriculum as the learners' progress upwards as well as achieving universal education for all.
- II. With the current full transition of students from one level to another, the problem of overcrowding still embeds itself despite being a new curriculum. Therefore, with the construction of new infrastructure being put in place, more funding should be put in place to have adequate infrastructure to accommodate the ever-increasing number of students.
- III. The competency-based curriculum has a framework of a self-assessment, the competency-based assessment (C.B.A.); therefore, a commission on that should be in place throughout to always review the curriculum and have an insight on whether it is meaningful to the Kenya education system.
- IV. Teachers, despite being trained on the curriculum, still face challenges with the contents of the new curriculum; therefore, reskilling the teachers is important and having more teachers is important to improve the teacher-learner ratio.
- V. As the respective agencies are training teachers, the teachers themselves should also show commitment to the implementation of the curriculum so as to facilitate the achievement of the stipulated objective of the new curriculum in Kenya.
- VI. The emphasis on teacher training and professional development highlights the need for ongoing support and resources to ensure that educators are adequately prepared to implement curriculum changes effectively.
- VII. Industrial and technological development should be incorporated into the curriculum at an early stage to equip learners with the necessary skills to be productive in the economy at a young age. This will account for the dropouts, which will reduce the waste of investment per student and thus make them productive people even after failing to resume their studies.
- VIII. With the current unemployment rate, the stakeholders should also put more emphasis on technical and vocational education so as to facilitate those who are willing to acquire knowledge in a given field to go back to this institution and thus produce more productive people in society rather than depending on the few employment opportunities available at the labour market.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Deakin Crick, R., & Joldersma, C. W. (2007). Habermas, lifelong learning and citizenship education. *Studies in Philosophy and Education*, pp. 26, 77–95.
- [2] Fomiškina, J., Woogen, E., Peiris, A., Abdulrazzak, S., & Cameron, E. (2021). Nurturing Every Learner's Potential: Education Reform in Kenya. *Implementing Deeper Learning and 21st Century Education Reforms: Building an Education Renaissance after a Global Pandemic*, 129-144.
- [3] K.I.C.D. (2016). Basic Education Curriculum Framework (B.E.C.F.). Nairobi, Kenya.
- [4] Ruth, C. (2019). "The 'Africanized' Competency Based Curriculum: The Twenty-First Century Strides." *Shan lax International Journal of Education*, vol. 7, no. 4, 2019, pp. 46–51.
- [5] L Kaviti, (2018). *The new curriculum of education in Kenya: A linguistic and education paradigm shift*. University of Nairobi (2018).
- [6] K.I.C.D. (2016). *A needs assessment Report of curriculum change*. Nairobi, Kenya.
- [7] East African Community (2014). *Harmonized curriculum structure and framework for the East African Community: Primary Education*, Arusha.
- [8] Dede, C. (2010). Comparing frameworks for 21st-century skills. *21st century skills: Rethinking how students learn*, 20(2010), 51-76.
- [9] Wanjohi, A. M. (2011). *Development of the education system in Kenya since independence*. K.E.N.P.R.O. Online Papers Portal, 5.
- [10] Lelei, M. C., & Weidman, J. C. (2012). *Education development in Kenya: Enhancing access and quality*. In *Quality and Qualities* (pp. 143-162). Brill Sense.
- [11] Wesselink, R., Biemans, H. J. A., Mulder, M., & van den Elsen, E. R. (2007). Competence-based V.E.T. as seen by Dutch researchers. *European Journal of Vocational Training*, 40(1), 40-55.
- [12] Amunga, J., Were D., & Ashioya, I. (2020). The Teacher-Parent Nexus in the Competency-Based Curriculum Success Equation in Kenya. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 12(1), 60-76.
- [13] Luan, W. S., & Bakar, K. A. (2008). The shift in the role of teachers in the learning process. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(2), 33-41.
- [14] Republic of Kenya (G.O.K.). (1964). *Kenya Education Commission*.
- [15] Sifuna, D. N & Obonyo, M. M. (2019). Competency-Based Curriculum in Primary Schools in Kenya - Prospects and Challenges of Implementation. *Journal of Popular Education in Africa*. 3(7), 39 – 50.
- [16] Brown, J. D., & Trotter, H. (2017). Stakeholder engagement in education reform: A systematic review of the literature. *Review of Educational Research*, 87(2), 378–410.
- [17] Chakraborty, M., & Nafukho, F. M. (2016). Competency-based education in higher education institutions: A scoping review. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 30(7), 1259–1274.
- [18] Kinshuk, C., N. S., C., I. L., & Chew, S. W. (2016). Evolution is not enough: Revolutionizing current learning environments to smart learning environments. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*, pp. 26, 561–581.
- [19] Mulder, M. (2006). Competence-based education and training: Does it help workforce development? *Journal of European Industrial Training*. 30(7), 569–589.
- [20] Gruppen, L. D., Burkhardt, J. C., Fitzgerald, J. T., Funnell, M., Haftel, H. M., Lypson, M. L., & Vasquez, J. A. (2016). Competency-based education: programme design and challenges to implementation. *Medical education*, 50(5), 532-539.

- [21] Gulled, Yasin. (2023). Paradigms for Contextualizing Competency Based Curriculum in Africa: Inferences from the O.E.C.D. Countries. *Education Quarterly Reviews*. 6. 464-475.
- [22] National Association of Colleges and Employers. (2020). *Job Outlook 2020: The Candidate Skills/Qualities Employers Want*. Retrieved from [www.nacweb.org].
- [23] Hargreaves, A., & Fullan, M. (2012). *Professional capital and the reform of education*. Teachers College Press.
- Fullan, M. (2016). *The new meaning of educational change*. Teachers College Press.
- [24] Levin, B. (2010). Educational reform and instructional change in Alberta. *Journal of Educational Change*, 11(1), 1–21.
- [25] Stokols, D., Hall, K. L., Taylor, B. K., & Moser, R. P. (2008). The science of team science: overview of the field and introduction to the supplement. *American journal of preventive medicine*, 35(2), S77-S89.
- [26] Cook, B. G., & Odom, S. L. (2013). Evidence-based practices and implementation science in special education. *Exceptional Children*, 79(2), 135-144.
- [27] Nutley, S., Walter, I., & Davies, H. T. (2003). From knowing to doing: A framework for understanding the evidence-into-practice agenda. *Evaluation*, 9(2), 125–148.
- [28] Bland, C. J., Starnaman, S., Wersal, L., Moorhead-Rosenberg, L., Zonia, S., & Henry, R. (2000). Curricular change in medical schools: how to succeed. *Academic medicine*, 75(6), 575–594.
- [29] Redman, A., & Wiek, A. (2021, November). Competencies for advancing transformations towards sustainability. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 6, p. 785163). Frontiers Media S.A.
- [30] Sahlberg, P. (2015). *Finnish Lessons 2.0: What can the world learn from educational change in Finland?* Teachers College Press.
- [31] Yang ZL, Wang J, Bonsall S, Fang QG. Use of fuzzy evidential reasoning in maritime security assessment. *Risk Analysis*, 2009; 29(1):95–120.

Mr. Mutai Ronald Kipsang received MSc from Nanjing Agricultural University, China.